

INVESTIGATION OF THE MOISTURE ABSORPTION BEHAVIOR OF GFRP EXPOSED TO MARINE ENVIRONMENT AND THE DEGRADATION OF ITS INTERLAMINAR SHEAR PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT

An innovative type of repair for offshore steel pipelines is adhesively-bonded laminate composite owing to its low self-weight and ease of manufacturing. However, it is of ultimate importance to monitor the degradation of the composite materials exposed to saltwater aging, provided that water molecules can diffuse into the polymer and along the fiber/matrix interface, leading to matrix plasticization, delamination and debonding. To study the moisture absorption of polymer composites, a laminated epoxy-matrix composite reinforced with bidirectional woven glass fibers was employed. The samples were subjected to accelerated salt spray aging at 35°C, 55°C, and 70°C with 5.0wt% NaCl diluted in water, followed by interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) tests to assess the mechanical degradation with time. It was seen from the experimental tests that temperature accelerates not only the moisture uptake, but also property degradation.

KEYWORDS

Glass-fiber laminate, saltwater aging, moisture absorption, interlaminar shear.

INTRODUCTION

Metallic pipelines are the safest long-distance means of transport for oil and gas resources due to its higher resistance, simplicity and low cost. However, these pipelines are prone to undergo deterioration due to corrosion caused by the exposure to aggressive media, like marine environments, leading to catastrophic failure [1,2]. Polymeric composites are a potential repair for metallic components and pipelines [3] due to its high resistance/weight ratio and high resistance to corrosion, leading to even greater advantages in comparison with conventional construction materials, like steel [4,5]. Besides, fiber reinforced polymer composites (FRP) are more easily processed for repairs in comparison with techniques using metals [6]. However, polymeric materials are also susceptible to moisture-induced degradation; therefore, the understanding of the degradation mechanism is crucial to assess the service-life of the composite repair.

The water penetration in the composites is mainly governed by the diffusion mechanism. Water penetrates the polymeric material mainly by diffusion of water molecules into the bulk matrix through micropores in the polymers, called free volumes [7,8]. Moisture can also penetrate the material through capillarity on the interface, and microcracks, voids and porosities at interfaces [9]. In glass-fiber reinforced polymers (GFRP), the constituent that absorbs most of the moisture is the polymer resin, while the glass fiber is hydrophobic. Since the absorption behavior is temperature-dependent, the higher the temperature, the higher the diffusivity, i.e., the absorption rate [10,11]. Some authors found out that the higher the temperature, the stronger the total moisture content, due to the proximity to the T_g [12–

14], whereas some authors dispute that the temperature does not affect the total moisture absorbed [15,16].

The moisture absorption of the glass-fiber and carbon-fiber reinforced polymeric composites causes, more importantly, the degradation of matrix-dominated properties, such as interlaminar and in-plane shear resistances [15]. The loss of these mechanical properties is mainly attributed to plasticization [7,15,17,18] and matrix swelling and its induced internal stresses [15,19–21], leading to fiber/matrix debonding and delamination [15,18,22]. An efficient test to evaluate interface degradation is ILSS (Interlaminar Shear Strength), in which a short-span flexural test is performed, also named SBS (Short Beam Shear). Some authors have reported degradation analyses with ILSS tests after exposure to both saltwater and distilled water environments [7,18,23,24]. These works report the initial strong decrease followed by a retention plateau, indicating a degradation level beyond which the material will not attain. Additionally, it is reported that the severity of the degradation increases with temperature; in other words, the higher the temperature, the lower the retention level.

Some analytical models have been developed by researchers to assess the mechanical degradation behavior of the materials. One of the most well-known models used in literature is the Phani and Bose model [25], described by Equation 1, where S is the strength retention at time t , S_{∞} is the long-term retention plateau, 100 is the retention of the unaged material and τ is the fitted parameter for this model. By applying Eq. 1 to the experimental data, the fitted parameters are found. In addition, the degradation rate (k) can be calculated by the inverse of the parameter τ , as shown in Equation 2.

$$S = (100 - S_{\infty})e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}} + S_{\infty} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$k(h^{-1}) = \frac{1}{\tau} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

This work aims at the investigation on the moisture-induced degradation on glass-fiber reinforced composites generally used in pipeline repairs. Therefore, the composite samples were exposed to salt spray (SS) environments in heated individual chambers at three temperatures: 35, 55 and 70°C. Gravimetric measurements were periodically taken on the samples to assess their mass change with time. Furthermore, ILSS samples were periodically withdrawn from the aging chambers to have their interlaminar shear properties evaluated.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Materials

The composite used in this work was fabricated using the same fabrication method as the conventional composite repair systems (hand lay-up lamination), consisting in a bidirectional glass-fiber woven embedded to an epoxy matrix. The woven has a 2:1 weft (66% longitudinal fibers and 33% transverse fibers) and a weight of 365 g/m². The laminates consist of twenty epoxy + glass fiber layers, for a total nominal thickness of 6.0 mm.

A PIPEFIX bicomponent epoxy resin (DGEBA epoxy resin + polyamine-based hardener) was used. This is a low-temperature cure resin, having a curing time of approximately 6 hours at 25°C. The laminates were initially fabricated in plates, and afterwards, cut into the desired samples' dimensions for the absorption and ILSS tests.

Methods

Aging

The composite samples were subjected to aging using three independent salt spray heating chambers EQUILAM SSEQ-Walk-In, working at temperatures of 35°C, 55°C and 70°C. All the temperature

values adopted are higher than room temperature in order to accelerate the hygrothermal aging of the materials. After some DMTA analyses, it was found that the T_g of the unaged composite fits within the range 86.74 – 100.15°C, therefore the highest temperature chamber (70°C) would be operating at a temperature closer to material's T_g , inducing in stronger chain modifications [26]. The salt concentration in the solution used for the SS chambers was 5.0 wt%, according to the recommendations of ASTM B117 standard [27].

Every two weeks the samples were withdrawn from the chambers to have their mass change measured by the gravitational method, according to Equation 3, where $M_{\%}$ is the percentage of water absorbed, M_t is the mass at a given time t and M_0 is the mass at time equal to zero, i.e., the unaged specimens. The total time span for the absorption measurements was 13510 hours. The mass change was measured using an analytical balance with a precision of 0.0001 g. After each withdrawal from the chambers, the samples were wrapped in a plastic film to mitigate the water loss in the transportation to the balance.

$$M_{\%} = \frac{M_t - M_0}{M_0} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

Four absorption laminate samples were fabricated for each chamber, summing a total of twelve absorption specimens. Their nominal dimensions were designated according to recommendations from the ASTM D570 standard [28], which are 76.2 mm x 25.4 mm x 6.0 mm (length x width x thickness).

Interlaminar Shear Test (ILSS)

The ILSS tests were performed according to the schedule shown in Table 1, where the letter T stands for *time*.

Terminology	Aging time (hours)
T0	Unaged (0 h)
T1	570 h
T2	1820 h
T3	3490 h
T4	5160 h
T5	6830 h
T6	8500 h
T7	10170 h
T8	11840 h
T9	13510 h

A servo hydraulic actuator MTS 810-500 with capacity of 500 kN was used. A 26-mm span was used between the supports and actuator displacement transducer was used for the analysis. Specimens were loaded at a displacement rate of 1 mm/min up to failure. For this test, fifteen samples were fabricated for each chamber and each aging time (Table 1) with dimensions designated by the ASTM D2344 standard [29], which are 36.0 mm x 12.0 mm x 6.0 mm (length x width x thickness). The interlaminar shear strength (σ) was calculated according to the Equation 4, where P is the peak load observed during the test, b is the specimen's width and h is the specimen's thickness.

$$\sigma = 0.75 \times \frac{P}{b \times h} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Absorption

Figure 1 shows the moisture absorption vs. aging time graph for the three temperatures tested. Each data point is an average value from four specimens. The withdrawals for the mechanical tests are represented in this graph.

Figure 1. Moisture uptake of composites as a function of aging time.

From Figure 1, it can be seen that, up to T2 (1820 hours), the specimens exposed to higher temperatures presented stronger absorption content. However, for longer aging times the absorption levels at higher temperatures were surpassed by that of 35°C. This behavior disagrees with literature [12–14] and can be explained by the post-cure phenomenon. Some works in literature state that the curing reaction between a DGEBA epoxy resin and a polyamine-based hardener decreases the availability of hydrophilic sites in the polymer matrix, curbing the water absorption [30–32].

Interlaminar Shear Strength Test

Figure 2 displays the ILSS retention level as a function of aging time for all temperatures tested. It can be seen that the higher temperatures promoted stronger degradation as the plateau retention level was lower at high temperatures. This property loss is due to the plasticization effect induced by humidity and the attack of water onto the fiber/matrix interface [11,33]. A sharp decrease in strength level at short aging time was observed, followed by an apparent degradation plateau. This is caused by the combined effects of the accelerated water absorption on the composites and the thermal effects on composite's integrity [23,34].

Figure 2. ILSS retention curves as a function of aging time.

By fitting Equation 1 onto the experimental data shown in Figure 2 by means of the least square method, the fitted parameters can be obtained. Figure 3 shows the experimental data and the fitted model. Table 2 shows the fitted parameters S_{∞} and τ for all three temperatures, as well as the degradation rate (k) calculated by Equation 2. It can be seen from both Figure 3 and Table 2 that, at 35 and 55°C, the degradation rates were roughly the same, while at 70°C the specimens showed a stronger degradation. Regarding the plateau retention level (S_{∞}), it decreased with temperature, although there was not a considerable drop in value. This means that, considering the standard deviations, the degradation plateau was nearly the same for all temperatures; therefore, temperature have little influence on the long-term damage, with the water being the dominant degradation factor.

Figure 3. ILSS Retention curves with fitted Phani and Bose model.

Table 2. Fitted parameters from Phani and Bose model.

Temperature (°C)	τ (h)	S_{∞} (%)	k (h^{-1})
35	1964.13	74.52	5.09×10^{-4}
55	1964.13	74.27	5.09×10^{-4}
70	319.05	70.58	3.13×10^{-3}

CONCLUSION

Temperature was shown to be an essential factor in accelerating composite degradation in harsh environments. It was seen that at higher temperatures, the composites presented a faster moisture absorption. It was also shown that the degradation rate did not differ between 35 and 55°C, increasing at 70°C, evidencing the higher degradation severity at higher temperatures.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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